

Appendix to Exploiting Large Language Models for the Automated Generation of Constraint Satisfaction Problems

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Abstract

Constraint Satisfaction Problems (CSPs) are a core technology that solves many real-world problems, especially for configuration tasks. A key success factor in this context is an efficient knowledge acquisition process where domain experts and knowledge engineers (developers of CSPs) should develop an agreement on the correctness of the expanding knowledge base as soon as possible. In this paper, we show how large language models (LLMs) can be applied to the automated generation of solutions for constraint satisfaction problems thus reducing overheads related to CSP development and maintenance in the future.

1. Introduction

This appendix presents the experiments including prompts and generated models¹.

2. Complete Dialog

System: tool Python_REPL, description: A Python shell. Use this to run and verify your solution to the constraint problem. Input should be a valid Python script using psychoco. The last line should be "verify_solutions(solutions, ...)" in order to verify your solutions. You are an agent designed to solve constraint problems, you write python code to solve and verify constraint problems. You have access to a python REPL, which you can use to execute python code and to verify your solution. If you get an error, debug your code and

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try again. You only use the constraint solver pychoco. you conclude your python code with a variable "solutions" and verify it with the method call "verify_solutions(solutions, <problem_name>)", where <problem_name> is given to you as the first word of the instructions. "solutions" should be a list of all solutions to the constraint problem. If verification fails, you correct your solution. Use the following example as a template for solving constraint problems with pychoco:

User: ints10. find numbers one to 10.

Assistant:

```
```python
from pychoco.model import Model
from test_tool import verify_solutions

model = Model()
x = model.intvar(1, 10, "x")
solver = model.get_solver()
solutions = verify_solutions(solutions, "ints10")
```
```

User: queen8. solve the 8-queen problem

Assistant:

Python_REPL (tool call):

```
1 from pychoco.model import Model
2 from test_tool import verify_solutions
3
4 model = Model("8-Queens Problem")
5
6 # Create an array of integer variables representing the position of each queen.
7 # Each variable has a domain from 1 to 8, representing the row number in a particular
8 # column.
9 queens = [model.intvar(1, 8, "queen_{}".format(i+1)) for i in range(8)]
10
11 # Add constraints
12 for i in range(8):
13     for j in range(i+1, 8):
14         model.all_different([queens[i], queens[j]]).post() # Different rows
15         model.arithm(queens[i], "!=", queens[j] + (j-i)).post() # Different
16         diagonals going down to the right
17         model.arithm(queens[i], "!=", queens[j] - (j-i)).post() # Different
18         diagonals going up to the right
19
20 # Find all solutions
21 solver = model.get_solver()
22 solutions = [s.get_int_vector(queens) for s in solver.find_all_solutions()]
23 verify_solutions(solutions, "queen8")
```

Python_REPL (tool response):

```
1 Traceback (most recent call last):
2   File "/tmp/tmpwltya0jz.py", line 19, in <module>
3     solutions = [s.get_int_vector(queens) for s in solver.find_all_solutions()]
4   File "/tmp/tmpwltya0jz.py", line 19, in <listcomp>
5     solutions = [s.get_int_vector(queens) for s in solver.find_all_solutions()]
6 AttributeError: 'Solution' object has no attribute 'get_int_vector'
```

Assistant: There seems to be a mistake in my code where I used an incorrect method to retrieve the solution vector. Let me correct this and try again.

Python_REPL (tool call):

```
1 from pychoco.model import Model
2 from test_tool import verify_solutions
3
4 model = Model("8-Queens Problem")
5
6 # Create an array of integer variables representing the position of each queen.
7 # Each variable has a domain from 1 to 8, representing the row number in a particular
8 # column.
9 queens = [model.intvar(1, 8, "queen_{}".format(i+1)) for i in range(8)]
10
11 # Constraints: no two queens can be in the same row, column, or diagonal.
12 model.all_different(queens).post()
13 for i in range(8):
14     for j in range(i+1, 8):
15         model.arithm(queens[i], "!=" , queens[j] + (j-i)).post() # Different
16         # diagonals going down to the right
17         model.arithm(queens[i], "!=" , queens[j] - (j-i)).post() # Different
18         # diagonals going up to the right
19
20 # Find all solutions
21 solver = model.get_solver()
22 solutions = []
23 while solver.solve():
24     solutions.append([solver.get_value(queens[i]) for i in range(8)])
25
26 verify_solutions(solutions, "queen8")
```

Python_REPL (tool response):

```
1 Traceback (most recent call last):
2   File "/tmp/tmpux2k6j7n.py", line 21, in <module>
3     solutions.append([solver.get_value(queens[i]) for i in range(8)])
4   File "/tmp/tmpux2k6j7n.py", line 21, in <listcomp>
5     solutions.append([solver.get_value(queens[i]) for i in range(8)])
6 AttributeError: 'Solver' object has no attribute 'get_value'
```

Assistant: I apologize for the mistake. I will correct the method for retrieving the value of the integer variables in the solution and try again.

Python_REPL (tool call):

```
1 from pychoco.model import Model
2 from test_tool import verify_solutions
3
4 model = Model("8-Queens Problem")
5
6 # Create an array of integer variables representing the position of each queen.
7 # Each variable has a domain from 1 to 8, representing the row number in a particular
8 # column.
9 queens = [model.intvar(1, 8, "queen_{}".format(i)) for i in range(8)]
10
11 # Constraints: no two queens can be in the same row, column, or diagonal.
12 model.all_different(queens).post()
13 for i in range(8):
14     for j in range(i+1, 8):
15         model.arithm(queens[i], "-", queens[j], "!=", j - i).post()
16         model.arithm(queens[i], "+", queens[j], "!=", j - i).post()
17
18 # Find all solutions
19 solver = model.get_solver()
20 solutions = []
21 while solver.solve():
22     solutions.append([solver.get_solution().get_int_val(queens[i]) for i in range(8)
23 ])
24
25 verify_solutions(solutions, "queen8")
```

Python_REPL (tool response):

```
1 Traceback (most recent call last):
2   File "/tmp/tmpo1rua9k3.py", line 21, in <module>
3     solutions.append([solver.get_solution().get_int_val(queens[i]) for i in range(8)
4 ])
5   File "/tmp/tmpo1rua9k3.py", line 21, in <listcomp>
6     solutions.append([solver.get_solution().get_int_val(queens[i]) for i in range(8)
7 ])
8 AttributeError: 'Solver' object has no attribute 'get_solution'. Did you mean: '
9 find_solution'?
```

Assistant: It appears I made another error in the method call to retrieve the solution. I will correct it and execute the code again.

Python_REPL (tool call):

```
1 from pychoco.model import Model
2 from test_tool import verify_solutions
```

```

3
4 model = Model("8-Queens Problem")
5
6 # Create an array of integer variables representing the position of each queen.
7 # Each variable has a domain from 1 to 8, representing the row number in a particular
   column.
8 queens = [model.intvar(1, 8, "queen_{}".format(i)) for i in range(8)]
9
10 # Constraints: no two queens can be in the same row, column, or diagonal.
11 model.all_different(queens).post()
12 for i in range(8):
13     for j in range(i+1, 8):
14         model.arithm(queens[i], "-", queens[j], "!=", j - i).post()
15         model.arithm(queens[i], "+", queens[j], "!=", j - i + 2).post()
16
17 # Find all solutions
18 solver = model.get_solver()
19 solutions = []
20 while solver.solve():
21     solutions.append([solver.get_int_val(queens[i]) for i in range(8)])
22
23 verify_solutions(solutions, "queen8")

```

Python_REPL (tool response):

```

1 Traceback (most recent call last):
2   File "/tmp/tmpuycteo67.py", line 21, in <module>
3     solutions.append([solver.get_int_val(queens[i]) for i in range(8)])
4   File "/tmp/tmpuycteo67.py", line 21, in <listcomp>
5     solutions.append([solver.get_int_val(queens[i]) for i in range(8)])
6 AttributeError: 'Solver' object has no attribute 'get_int_val'

```

Assistant: There was yet another mistake in the method to retrieve the value of an integer variable from the solver. I will correct it and try again.

Python_REPL (tool call):

```

1 from pychoco.model import Model
2 from test_tool import verify_solutions
3
4 model = Model("8-Queens Problem")
5
6 # Create an array of integer variables representing the position of each queen.
7 # Each variable has a domain from 1 to 8, representing the row number in a particular
   column.
8 queens = [model.intvar(1, 8, "queen_{}".format(i+1)) for i in range(8)]
9
10 # Add constraints
11 for i in range(8):
12     for j in range(i+1, 8):
13         model.all_different([queens[i], queens[j]]).post() # Different rows

```

```

14     model.arithm(queens[i], "!=" , queens[j], "+", j-i).post() # Different
      diagonals going down to the right
15     model.arithm(queens[i], "!=" , queens[j], "-", j-i).post() # Different
      diagonals going up to the right
16
17 # Find all solutions
18 solver = model.get_solver()
19 solutions = []
20 while solver.solve():
21     solutions.append([solver.get_var_value(queens[i]) for i in range(8)])
22
23 verify_solutions(solutions, "queen8")

```

Python_REPL (tool response):

```

1 Traceback (most recent call last):
2   File "/tmp/tmpHzqe8_ih.py", line 21, in <module>
3     solutions.append([solver.get_var_value(queens[i]) for i in range(8)])
4   File "/tmp/tmpHzqe8_ih.py", line 21, in <listcomp>
5     solutions.append([solver.get_var_value(queens[i]) for i in range(8)])
6 AttributeError: 'Solver' object has no attribute 'get_var_value'

```

Assistant: I apologize for the repeated errors. I will correct the method for retrieving the value of integer variables from the solution again and ensure it is accurate this time.

Python_REPL (tool call):

```

1 from pchoco.model import Model
2 from test_tool import verify_solutions
3
4 model = Model("8-Queens Problem")
5
6 # Create an array of integer variables representing the position of each queen.
7 # Each variable has a domain from 1 to 8, representing the row number in a particular
8 # column.
9 queens = [model.intvar(1, 8, "queen_{}".format(i)) for i in range(8)]
10
11 # Constraints: no two queens can be in the same row, column, or diagonal.
12 model.all_different(queens).post()
13 for i in range(8):
14     for j in range(i+1, 8):
15         model.arithm(queens[i], "-", queens[j], "=", j - i).post()
16         model.arithm(queens[i], "+", queens[j], "=", j - i).post()
17
18 # Find all solutions
19 solver = model.get_solver()
20 solutions = []
21 while solver.solve():
22     solutions.append([queens[i].get_value() for i in range(8)])
23
24 verify_solutions(solutions, "queen8")

```

Python_REPL (tool response):

```
1 10 of the 746 solutions are correct. Expected 92 solutions
```

Assistant: It appears that the previous code is not generating all the correct solutions as expected. I will revise the code to ensure that all constraints are correctly implemented and all solutions are found. Let me fix and run the code once more.

Python_REPL (tool call):

```
1 from pychoco.model import Model
2 from test_tool import verify_solutions
3
4 model = Model("8-Queens Problem")
5
6 # Create an array of integer variables representing the position of each queen.
7 # Each variable has a domain from 1 to 8, representing the row number in a particular
8   column.
9 queens = [model.intvar(1, 8, "queen_{}".format(i+1)) for i in range(8)]
10
11 # Constraints: no two queens can be in the same row, column, or diagonal.
12 model.all_different(queens).post()
13 for i in range(8):
14     for j in range(i+1, 8):
15         model.arithm(queens[i], "-", queens[j], "!=", j - i).post() # Different
16         diagonals
17         model.arithm(queens[i], "-", queens[j], "!=", i - j).post() # Different
18         diagonals
19
20 # Find all solutions
21 solver = model.get_solver()
22 solutions = []
23 while solver.solve():
24     solutions.append([queens[i].get_value() for i in range(8)])
25
26 verify_solutions(solutions, "queen8")
```

Python_REPL (tool response):

```
1 92 of the 92 solutions are correct. Expected 92 solutions
```

Assistant: All 92 solutions to the 8-Queen problem have been found and verified as correct.

3. Solution for the Three Queens Model

Used LLM: ChatGPT-4.

```

1 python
2 from pycoco.model import Model
3 # Create a model
4 model = Model()
5 # Define the number of queens
6 n = 3
7 # Create an array of variables representing the queen's position in each row
8 queens = model.intvars(n, 1, n, "queens")
9 # Add constraints to ensure queens do not attack each other diagonally or horizontally
10 for i in range(n):
11     for j in range(i + 1, n):
12         model.arithm(queens[i], "!=" , queens[j]).post()
13         model.arithm(queens[i], "-", queens[j], "!=" , j - i).post()
14         model.arithm(queens[i], "+", queens[j], "!=" , j - i).post()
15 # Solve the model and display the solution if one exists
16 solver = model.get_solver()
17 solution = solver.find_solution()
18 if solution:
19     for i in range(n):
20         print(f'Queen {i+1}: Row {i+1}, Column {solution.get_int_val(queens[i])}')
21     else:
22         print('No solution found.')
```

4. Solution for the 8-Queens Model

Used LLM: ChatGPT 4.

```

1 from pycoco.model import Model
2 from test_tool import verify_solutions
3 model = Model("8-Queens Problem")
4 # Create an array of integer variables representing the position of each queen.
5 # Each variable has a domain from 1 to 8, representing the row number in a particular
6 # column.
7 queens = [model.intvar(1, 8, "queen_{}".format(i+1)) for i in range(8)]
8 # Constraints: no two queens can be in the same row, column, or diagonal.
9 model.all_different(queens).post()
10 for i in range(8):
11     for j in range(i+1, 8):
12         model.arithm(queens[i], "-", queens[j], "!=" , j - i).post() # Different diagonals
13         model.arithm(queens[i], "-", queens[j], "!=" , i - j).post() # Different diagonals
14 # Find all solutions
15 solver = model.get_solver()
16 solutions = []
17 while solver.solve():
18     solutions.append([queens[i].get_value() for i in range(8)])
19
20 verify_solutions(solutions, "queen8")
```

5. Solution for Map Coloring

Used LLM: ChatGPT 4.

```
1 from pychoco.model import Model
2 from test_tool import verify_solutions
3
4 model = Model()
5 regions = ['A', 'B', 'C', 'D']
6 adjacency_list = {
7     'A': ['B', 'C'],
8     'B': ['A', 'C', 'D'],
9     'C': ['A', 'B', 'D'],
10    'D': ['B', 'C']
11 }
12 colors = range(3)
13
14 # Create a variable for each region
15 color_vars = {region: model.intvar(0, len(colors)-1, region) for region in regions}
16
17 # Add constraints for each edge in the adjacency list
18 for region, neighbors in adjacency_list.items():
19     for neighbor in neighbors:
20         model.all_different([color_vars[region], color_vars[neighbor]]).post()
21
22 solver = model.get_solver()
23 solutions = []
24 for s in solver.find_all_solutions():
25     solution = {region: s.get_int_val(color_vars[region]) for region in regions}
26     solutions.append(solution)
27
28 verify_solutions(solutions, "coloring")
```

6. Solution for TSP

Used LLM: ChatGPT 4.

```
1 from pychoco.model import Model
2 from test_tool import verify_solutions
3
4 # Number of cities
5 C = 4
6
7 # Distance matrix
8 D = [[0, 10, 15, 20], [10, 0, 35, 25], [15, 35, 0, 30], [20, 25, 30, 0]]
9
10 model = Model()
11
12 # Create an array of integer variables representing the next city to visit (circuit)
```

```

13 next_city = [model.intvar(0, C-1, f"next_city_{i}") for i in range(C)]
14
15 # Add the circuit constraint
16 model.circuit(next_city).post()
17
18 # Create a variable for the total distance
19 total_distance = model.intvar(0, sum(sum(row) for row in D), "total_distance")
20
21 # Add constraints for the total distance
22 distance_vars = []
23 for i in range(C):
24     distance = model.intvar(0, max(max(row) for row in D), f"dist_{i}")
25     model.element(distance, D[i], next_city[i]).post()
26     distance_vars.append(distance)
27
28 model.sum(distance_vars, "=", total_distance).post()
29
30 solver = model.get_solver()
31 solutions = []
32
33 while solver.solve():
34     # Retrieve the solution as a tour
35     tour = [0]
36     current = next_city[0].get_value()
37     while current != 0:
38         tour.append(current)
39         current = next_city[current].get_value()
40     solutions.append(tour)
41
42 verify_solutions(solutions, "tsp")

```

7. Tool Descriptions before Improvement

Before we improved the tool description in the prompt, in the chats related to the Map Coloring problem, several issues occur. The first chat (`./chats/coloring_20240516084111.txt`) contains syntax errors and fails to call the verify function, which is essential for validating the solution. Similarly, the next chat (`./chats/coloring_20240516084918.txt`) also exhibits syntax errors and does not submit the solution correctly, which hampers the overall process. Additionally, `./chats/coloring_20240516090424.txt` includes wrong API calls on PyChoco, further complicating the task of obtaining a valid solution. A final chat (`./chats/coloring_20240516090645.txt`) computes a correct run with no problems.

8. Occurred Errors

Following table show the errors which occur in several chats (FileName) during the creation of the TSP problem. Each error occurred multiple times.

| FileName | Error |
|--|--|
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106
preview_20240529090726.txt | TypeError: list indices must be integers
or slices, not IntVar |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106
preview_20240529090726.txt | AssertionError: IV_1 is not instantiated |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106
preview_20240529090726.txt | AttributeError: 'Model' object has no attribute
'subcircuit'. Did you mean: 'sub_circuit'? |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106
preview_20240529090726.txt | TypeError: 'str' object cannot be interpreted as
an integer |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106
preview_20240529090726.txt | AttributeError: 'Model' object has no attribute
'if_then_else' |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106
preview_20240529091641.txt | ModuleNotFoundError: No module named
'psychoco.objects.graphconstructors' |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106
preview_20240529091641.txt | ModuleNotFoundError: No module named
'psychoco.graphs' |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106
preview_20240529091641.txt | ImportError: cannot import name
'GraphVarFactory' from 'psychoco.variables' |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106
preview_20240529091641.txt | ImportError: cannot import name
'graphvars' from 'psychoco.variables' |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106
preview_20240529091641.txt | AttributeError: 'Model' object has no
attribute 'minimize' |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106
preview_20240529091641.txt | ImportError: cannot import name 'IntVar'
from 'psychoco.variables' |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106
preview_20240529091641.txt | AttributeError: 'Model' object has no
attribute 'if_then' |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106
preview_20240529091641.txt | TypeError: IntConstraintFactory.circuit()
takes from 2 to 4 positional arguments but 5 were given |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106
preview_20240529091641.txt | AttributeError: 'Model' object has no
attribute 'intvararray' |

Table 1
Error Log

9. Number of Tool Calls

The following tables document the number of calls to the Python tool as well as the number of text messages produced by the LLM.

| FileName | Error |
|---|--|
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106
preview_20240529091641.txt | AttributeError: 'Model' object has no attribute 'if_then_else' |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106
preview_20240529092718.txt | TypeError: list indices must be integers or slices, not IntVar |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106
preview_20240529093831.txt | TypeError: in method 'intvar_sii', argument 2 of type 'char **' |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-turbo
2024-04-09-_20240529102829.txt | TypeError: in method 'element_iv_ivarray_iv_i', argument 5 of type 'int' |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-turbo
2024-04-09-_20240529102829.txt | AssertionError: city_0 is not instantiated |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-turbo
2024-04-09-_20240529102829.txt | AttributeError: 'Model' object has no attribute 'offset' |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-turbo
2024-04-09-_20240529102829.txt | TypeError: in method 'int_offset_view', argument 2 of type 'int' |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-turbo
2024-04-09-_20240529103506.txt | AssertionError: conf must be in ['LIGHT', 'FIRST', 'RD', 'ALL'] |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-turbo
2024-04-09-_20240529103506.txt | TypeError: IntConstraintFactory.sub_circuit() takes 4 positional arguments but 5 were given |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4o-2024-05-13
-_20240529114219.txt | TypeError: IntConstraintFactory.element() missing 1 required positional argument: 'index' |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4o-2024-05-13
-_20240529114219.txt | AttributeError: 'Solver' object has no attribute 'get_value' |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4o-2024-05-13
-_20240529114219.txt | AttributeError: 'Solver' object has no attribute 'get_solution'.
Did you mean: 'find_solution'? |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4o-2024-05-13
-_20240529114219.txt | AttributeError: 'Solver' object has no attribute 'get_last_solution' |

Table 2
Error Log continued

| FileName | Tool Calls | Text Messages |
|--|------------|---------------|
| coloring_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106-preview_20240529094847.txt | 2 | 2 |
| coloring_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106-preview_20240529095157.txt | 1 | 1 |
| coloring_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106-preview_20240529095402.txt | 3 | 1 |
| coloring_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106-preview_20240529095612.txt | 3 | 3 |

Table 3
Tool calls and text messages for Map Coloring

| FileName | Tool Calls | Text Messages |
|--|------------|---------------|
| queen8_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106-preview_20240529094110.txt | 6 | 6 |
| queen8_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106-preview_20240529094303.txt | 2 | 1 |
| queen8_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106-preview_20240529094451.txt | 1 | 1 |
| queen8_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106-preview_20240529094710.txt | 7 | 7 |

Table 4
Tool calls and text messages for N-Queens

| FileName | Tool Calls | Text Messages |
|--|------------|---------------|
| square_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106-preview_20240529095955.txt | 6 | 3 |
| square_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106-preview_20240529100230.txt | 2 | 3 |
| square_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106-preview_20240529100358.txt | 2 | 1 |

Table 5
Tool calls and text messages for Square

| FileName | Tool Calls | Text Messages |
|--|------------|---------------|
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106-preview_20240529090726.txt | 15 | 14 |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106-preview_20240529091641.txt | 15 | 0 |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106-preview_20240529092718.txt | 15 | 14 |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-1106-preview_20240529093831.txt | 15 | 14 |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-turbo-2024-04-09-_20240529102829.txt | 15 | 15 |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4-turbo-2024-04-09-_20240529103506.txt | 15 | 15 |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4o-2024-05-13-_20240529112928.txt | 0 | 1 |
| tsp_cs_agent_sol2_gpt-4o-2024-05-13-_20240529114219.tx | 14 | 15 |

Table 6
Tool calls and text messages for TSP